

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract. The rapid development of statehood and trade encouraged the improvement of military works necessary for the defense of many small states, primarily for the construction of artillery and fortifications, as well as hydraulic engineering and architectural structures. Knowledge becomes a very real power in the society of that time. During the renaissance, a new social stratum was formed - a class of consulting engineers freed from the craft organization.

Key words: technology, mechanics, defense, crafts, military.

Annotatsiya. Davlatchilik va savdo-sotiqning jadal rivojlanishi ko'plab kichik davlatlar mudofaasi, birinchi navbatda artilleriya va istehkomlar, shuningdek, gidrotexnika va arxitektura inshootlarini qurish uchun zarur bo'lgan harbiy ishlarni takomillashtirishga turtki bo'ldi. Bilim o'sha davr jamiyatida juda haqiqiy kuchga aylanadi. Uyg'onish davrida yangi ijtimoiy qatlam - hunarmandchilik tashkilotidan ozod qilingan maslahatchi muhandislar sinfi shakllandi.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, mexanika, mudofaa, hunarmandchilik, harbiy.

Аннотация. Быстрое развитие государственности и торговли способствовало совершенствованию военных работ, необходимых для обороны многих малых государств, прежде всего для строительства артиллерии и укреплений, а также гидротехнических и архитектурных сооружений. Знание становится вполне реальной силой в обществе того времени. В эпоху Возрождения сформировался новый социальный слой — класс инженеров-консультантов, освободившихся от ремесленной организации.

Ключевые слова: техника, механика, оборона, ремесла, военное дело.

We can try to reconstruct the procedures of such technological activity using the tools of modern science, but it itself was directly transmitted in the process of reproduction, repetition, and its description can only be understood by the mythological mind, is a reflection of worldview.

As an example, you can learn the technique of making knives from Damascus steel. Accurate reconstruction of the ancient technology was made possible thanks to the development of modern nanotechnology, which made it possible to understand, explain and reproduce its procedures. Nanowires several hundreds of nanometers long, which have not been observed before, were found in the structure of a blade made of Damascus steel. However, this does not change the essence of the matter at all. In both cases, we are dealing with the description of the continuous side of technical activity, that is, with technology. In ancient times, a rational way of describing technology was formed. Applying mathematics in mechanics, not in physics, was effective. An Archimedean spiral is a curve formed by the movement of a point along a line, as the trajectory of a rectilinear and identical (relative) point, participating in two movements along a straight line. It can be determined that a part of it rotates around uniformly. The tips have a "pure mechanical character" from Archimedes' proof, meaning they are inspired by practical mechanics (Archimedes' screw). "If any straight line in a plane rotates uniformly around one of its ends, returns to its original position, and at the same time a certain point moves uniformly along the rotating straight line, leaving the fixed end, then this point in the said plane describes a spiral."

Ancient mechanics distinguished the so-called simple machines from which complex ones are assembled. Each of these machines (block, screw, chain hoist, etc.) corresponded to certain calculation methods. But assembling complex machines from them was not so easy even in modern times. Many engineers and scientists, including Galileo, worked on this problem. However, this problem really predates the science of machinery in the late 18th century, when the number of machines and

mechanisms increased so much that their descriptions took place in voluminous books.

According to Aristotle, "people are wise not because of their ability to act, but because they have understanding and know the reasons", "a leader is wiser than a craftsman, and speculative (theoretical) sciences are higher than wisdom." "Creators", "wisdom is greater than knowledge, it is chosen not for its consequences, but for its own benefit and the goal of knowledge." Indeed, the goal of theoretical knowledge is truth and the goal of practical knowledge is practice. If people consider things as they are, they do not consider eternity, but take the object in relation to something in the present. But we do not know the truth, its reason.

We should emphasize the decisive innovative role of engineering knowledge in the Middle Ages in the field of technical and economic organization (for example, the organization of the distribution of time and its use). Due to the development of science and technology, the combination of theoretical and practical components in the thinking of social life in the person of the Middle Ages was rare. Orientation to experience has gradually entered the field of philosophical consciousness. Of course, the medieval scholastics, as we know, were not interested in the objects themselves, but in the comparison of ideas and opinions about these objects. However, many debates about abstract concepts have strengthened the theoretical foundations of science, the ability to turn facts into concepts and to think rigorously based on a few general rules. Early medieval scholars Aurelius Augustine, Thomas Aquinas, Roger Bacon declared things as the source of knowledge. This approach to experience was best expressed by Roger Bacon: "There are two ways of knowing: by proof and by experience. Evidence leads us to a conclusion, but when the path of experience does not lead us to the truth, it does not confirm or dispel doubts in such a way that the soul is at peace in the contemplation of the truth. According to Roger Bacon, the line of knowledge, which he called experimental, comes from things that affect the senses. In addition, this effect can be independent of or subordinate to thinking. As a result, knowledge of the empirical order (intuitive, visual, etc.) is obtained. In his

opinion, "nothing can be known adequately without experience", that is, in knowing "arguments are not enough, experience is needed." Bacon illustrates this with the following example. If a person who has never seen fire tries to think that fire burns and destroys things, his mind will not be satisfied until he puts his hand into the fire or throws some inflammable substance into it, when he examines what his mind has led to for an experiment. Therefore, everything should be tested with experience. As we can see, the attitude towards the experimental science, which provides "perfect knowledge" and is considered to have great advantages over other sciences, is changing, its priority is justified by its "great utility". Such an understanding is directly opposed to Aristotle's classification of sciences, according to which the least useful science is considered the best and highest. Roger Bacon says that experimental science shows how to make wonderful instruments and how to use them after they have been made, and to tell all the mysteries of nature for the benefit of the state and individuals, and commands the other sciences as its servants. Such a campaign for experimental science was the result of a change in the worldview of the Middle Ages, from the ideal of direct contemplation of the truth without interfering with the affairs of nature, and the transition to the manipulation of natural objects in order to achieve true knowledge.

The rapid development of statehood and trade encouraged the improvement of military works necessary for the defense of many small states, primarily for the construction of artillery and fortifications, as well as hydraulic engineering and architectural structures. Improvements in artillery and fortifications were crucial to the existence and independence of the city-republics, as their independence often depended on the accuracy, range, and strength of fortifications. With the development of the wealth of these countries, the need for the construction of comfortable and beautiful architectural structures and the production of various machines that played the role of entertainment mechanisms and automata also increased. New scientific consulting engineers were needed everywhere, and they were highly valued by kings, dukes, townspeople. And simple craftsmanship was no

longer enough to carry out these activities. Therefore, the first engineers and inventors who solved technical problems turned to mathematics and mechanics for help, and gained new knowledge and skills in calculating methods. If this knowledge was not sufficient, they sought to acquire it themselves, and often became very effective scientists. Knowledge becomes a very real power in the society of that time. During the renaissance, a new social stratum was formed - a class of consulting engineers freed from the craft organization. First there are self-taught engineers who, due to the lack of engineering education, install water and windmills, pumps, fountains, repair mechanisms and supervise the creation of these mechanisms. These people usually knew arithmetic and partial mechanics, they were able to draw projects and perform elementary calculations. However, they gradually not only significantly expanded their knowledge, but became encyclopedically developed scientists and occupied an important place in the society of that time. The first engineers often served as teachers, gathered students around them, and even founded entire schools of scientific arts and crafts.

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